

Least-squares estimation of $B(t)$ by splines [IDT photometry]

L Lindegren 85-02-15

(1)

For simplicity consider a spline consisting of 1st-order polynomials (straight-line segments):

This can be regarded as a linear combination of 'Basic splines' $U_i(t)$, $i=1$ to n :

namely:

$$B(t) = \sum_{i=1}^n B_i U_i(t)$$

$$= B_i U_i(t) + B_{i+1} U_{i+1}(t) \quad \text{if } t_i \leq t \leq t_{i+1}$$

where, actually, $B_i = B(t_i)$ are the spline coefficients.

[Higher-order splines can similarly be constructed in terms of basisplines, but then there is no such simple relation as $B_i = B(t_i)$ for the spline coefficients, because the basis-splines are then overlapping adjacent knots.]

Now let $\hat{\beta}_1, \hat{\beta}_2$ be the IDT-measurements at time t . The model used is:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \beta_1 &= B(t) + I_s \\ \beta_2 &= M_1(w, z, c) I_s \end{aligned} \right\}$$

where I_s is a parameter for the star in this frame [i.e., we do not use that $I_s = \text{const}$ for a certain star] and (2)

$$M_1(w, z, c) = \tilde{M}_1 + \Delta M_1 + \Delta M_2 w + \Delta M_3 z + \Delta M_4 c + \Delta M_5 w^2 + \dots$$

[$c = (B-V) - 0.5$]. $\tilde{M}_1$ is the a priori modulation, which should be a function of c at least. ΔM_j are correction terms.

OBSERVATION EQNS:

Let $\tilde{I}_s$ be an approximate flux value [a priori or perhaps $\tilde{I}_s = \hat{\beta}_2 / \tilde{M}_1$] and ΔI_s , ΔM [= $\Delta M_1 + \Delta M_2 w + \dots$] the required corrections to $\tilde{I}_s$ and $\tilde{M}_1$. Then

$$\left. \begin{aligned} B(t) + \Delta I_s &= \hat{\beta}_1 - \tilde{I}_s \\ \tilde{M}_1 \Delta I_s + \tilde{I}_s \Delta M &= \hat{\beta}_2 - \tilde{M}_1 \tilde{I}_s \end{aligned} \right\}$$

Eliminating ΔI_s (which is permitted, since ΔI_s will only appear in these two obs. eqns) we get

$$B(t) - \frac{\tilde{I}_s}{\tilde{M}_1} \Delta M = \hat{\beta}_1 - \frac{1}{\tilde{M}_1} \hat{\beta}_2$$

which in terms of the ~~the~~ actual unknowns β_i and ΔM_j is:

$$\beta_i U_i(t) + \beta_{i+1} U_{i+1}(t) - \sum_{j=1}^N \left(\frac{\tilde{I}_s}{\tilde{M}_1} \right) f_j \Delta M_j = \hat{\beta}_1 - \frac{1}{\tilde{M}_1} \hat{\beta}_2 \quad (1)$$

if $t_i \leq t \leq t_{i+1}$, where $f_1 = 1$, $f_2 = w$, $f_3 = z$, $f_4 = c$, etc. and

$$\left. \begin{aligned} U_i(t) &= \frac{t_{i+1} - t}{t_{i+1} - t_i} \\ U_{i+1}(t) &= 1 - U_i(t) \end{aligned} \right\}$$

The variance of the rhs $\tilde{B} = \hat{\beta}_1 - \frac{1}{\tilde{M}_1} \hat{\beta}_2$ is given by NDAC/LO/026 eqn. (53)

with $\sigma_{\tilde{M}_1} = 0$.

Now for the SM observations at time t^* , we have background estimates $\hat{b}_B$ and $\hat{b}_V$ and assume

$$B(t^*) = c_0 + c_1 \hat{b}_B + c_2 \hat{b}_V$$

with c_0, c_1, c_2 additional unknowns. Unfortunately, the observations $\hat{b}_B, \hat{b}_V$ cannot be expressed in terms of the parametrized model $[B(t)]$, but a reasonable "observation equation" can nevertheless be obtained simply as

$$U_i(t^*) B_i + U_{i+1}(t^*) B_{i+1} - c_0 - \hat{b}_B c_1 - \hat{b}_V c_2 = 0 \quad (2)$$

in which $\hat{b}_B$ and $\hat{b}_V$ are regarded as known coefficients.

This is slightly inappropriate (because of the noise in $\hat{b}_B, \hat{b}_V$), but I think this should still work. The variance of the observation equation

is $\approx \tilde{c}_1^2 \sigma_{b_B}^2 + \tilde{c}_2^2 \sigma_{b_V}^2$ where $\tilde{c}_1, \tilde{c}_2$ are approximate values for the coefficients.

Comments: The form of (1) is interesting: the rhs is the simplest background estimate $\tilde{B} = \hat{\beta}_1 - \frac{1}{M_1} \hat{\beta}_2$ but the important thing is how this quantity is interpreted in the left-hand side. For faint stars ($I_S \approx 0$), $\tilde{B}$ is simply used as an observation of $B(t)$, while for bright stars (when the terms under the summation sign dominates) the right-hand side is mainly interpreted in terms of corrections to M_1 . The nice thing is that (1) gives the proper balance between these two extreme cases for any given star. It is of course still necessary to have a wide spread of I_S -values in order to separate the background and modulation effects, but it is not required to go to extreme values to ensure complete separation between the factors.

Finally, a few words about the structure of the normal equations. For linear splines, they are tridiagonal, with a border of width $N+3$ (N = number of parameters for DM):

If this special structure is taken advantage of for storing the normals and in the Cholesky solution, it is possible to have a large number of knots (perhaps up to 1000) with the entire system in primary

memory and a very quick solution.